

Forest to Fashion: Harnessing Bamboo's Sustainability in Eco-printing and Textile Design

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Abstract

In the ever-evolving apparel and home textile market, a plethora of new fibers has emerged, offering enhanced qualities and functionalities to the existing fabric range. Among these innovative materials, bamboo stands out as a noteworthy addition. Its cultivation requires significantly less water compared to cotton, making it particularly advantageous in water-scarce regions. What makes bamboo truly remarkable is its sustainable harvesting process, which allows for selective harvesting without causing deforestation. Unlike hardwood trees, bamboo can be harvested without the need to cut down the entire plant. As the industry strives to adopt more environmentally friendly practices, careful consideration is being given to the dyeing and finishing processes of various materials. In this context, eco-friendly alternatives are gaining prominence. One such solution is eco-printing, which involves the use of organic materials derived from nature to infuse prints onto surfaces. This eco-friendly approach to printing aligns with the industry's conscious choices and sustainable objectives. With a focus on exploring the background of bamboo textiles, a comprehensive study was undertaken. The objective was to design an ensemble that not only incorporates the value addition of eco-printing but also embraces the emerging trend of minimalism. By combining the benefits of bamboo textiles and eco-printing, the aim was to create a sustainable and aesthetically pleasing ensemble that resonates with the evolving preferences of conscious consumers.

Keywords: Bamboo, eco-printing, marigold, apparel, sustainability, summer wear

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1. Introduction

Bamboo, a renewable plant with a short growth cycle of 3 to 5 years, offers a sustainable solution for textile applications due to its minimal resource consumption. It has gained popularity in the mainstream textiles and apparel industry, thanks to its remarkable qualities such as softness, comfort, moisture-wicking, antimicrobial properties, thermoregulation, and UV protection. In line with the industry's growing focus on sustainability, the textile wet processing stage, known for its pollution caused by synthetic dyes and hazardous chemicals, is shifting towards eco-friendly dyeing and printing methods.

Against this backdrop, a study was undertaken to explore the potential of bamboo fabric and create a summer ensemble using eco-printing as an additional value proposition. The research paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the bamboo plant, covering its historical background, production methods, inherent properties, and diverse application areas. Furthermore, it highlights popular brands that have embraced bamboo textiles, along with an in-depth exploration of eco-printing techniques and its aesthetic aspects in the realm of slow fashion.

The study aims to contribute valuable insights into the sustainable utilization of bamboo textiles, showcasing its versatility and eco-friendly characteristics. By incorporating eco-printing, the research strives to demonstrate how innovative and environmentally conscious techniques can enhance the creation of fashionable ensembles suitable for the summer season.

2. Understanding the selected fabric: 100% Bamboo

2.1 The plant

Bamboo is one of the fastest-growing plants on Earth with some species capable of growing up to 91 cm (36 inches) in a single day. It can reach full maturity soon while trees used for traditional timber can take decades to grow (Fig.1). This fast growth makes bamboo a highly renewable resource based on which products can be planned and they grow back quickly [1]. Bamboo cultivation generally requires minimal water, pesticides, and fertilizers compared to other crops. It can also grow in diverse climates and soil conditions without the need for synthetic inputs [2].

Bamboo has an extensive root system that helps prevent soil erosion and promotes water retention. The plant's dense growth and leaf litter contribute to the enrichment of soil organic matter [3]. It is cultivated on marginal or degraded lands, revitalizing the soil and preventing further degradation. On cultivation, bamboo also has the ability to absorb large amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere and release oxygen. It is estimated that bamboo can sequester up to four times more CO₂ compared to hardwood trees. This makes bamboo plantations valuable in mitigating climate change and reducing greenhouse gas emissions [4, 5]. The cultivation is thus very helpful for the ecosystem and utilising the grown-up plants for textiles can be beneficial considering its biodegradable nature [6, 7].

Figure 1 – Growth of Bamboo Plant

Image Source: [https:// www.wilsonbrosgardens.com/propagation-of-bamboo-plants.html](https://www.wilsonbrosgardens.com/propagation-of-bamboo-plants.html)

2.2. History of Bamboo Textiles

The first known application of bamboo as a textile can be traced back to ancient civilizations in Asia, particularly in China. Bamboo has been used as a source of fibers for weaving into textiles for thousands of years. In China, historical records suggest that bamboo textiles were in use as early as the Ming Dynasty (13th – 16th century) and Qing Dynasty (16th -19th century). During this time, bamboo fibers were manually extracted from bamboo stalks and processed into yarn for weaving. Bamboo fibers are naturally soft, lightweight, and breathable, making them suitable for clothing and other textile applications. The traditional process of making bamboo textiles involved several steps. First, the bamboo stalks were harvested and soaked in water to soften them. Then, the outer layer of the stalks was removed, and the remaining material was mechanically crushed to extract the fibers. These fibers were then spun into yarn and woven into textiles using traditional weaving techniques. These were used for clothing, bedding, and household items such as mats and baskets. The use of bamboo textiles gradually spread beyond China to other parts of Asia, including Japan and Southeast Asian countries. One notable development in bamboo textile production occurred in the early 2000s when a Chinese company named Beijing Sen Li Da Xie Chemical Fiber Technology Co., Ltd. patented a bamboo fiber extraction method. This method involved using a combination of chemical and mechanical processes to produce bamboo viscose fibers suitable for textile production [8].

2.3. Production of Bamboo textiles

Bamboo fabric is derived from the bamboo plant, specifically the pulp of the bamboo stalks. In order to robust its textile quality, it is important to harvest bamboo at the right time and ensure optimal fiber quality. The quality and durability of bamboo fabric can vary depending on the manufacturing process and the specific brand. High-quality bamboo fabric can be durable and long-lasting, with the ability to withstand regular washing and wear.

Bamboo plant shoots are collected, chopped and the harvested bamboo culms (stems) are split or crushed to extract the bamboo fibers (Fig.2). This is done in two ways;

i). **Mechanical Processing:** In this method, the bamboo culms are crushed and mechanically scraped to separate the fibers from the woody parts. The fibers are then mechanically combed to remove impurities and prepare them for further processing.

ii). **Chemical Processing:** In this method, the bamboo culms are treated with chemicals, such as sodium hydroxide, to break down the lignin and hemicellulose components. This process is known as "retting" and helps to release the fibers. The fibers are then mechanically extracted and cleaned [2, 9]. Bleaching and dyeing is an optional step after extraction, where the bamboo fibers may undergo a bleaching process to achieve a desired whiteness or color. Dyeing may also be performed to add color to the fibers before they are spun into yarn or used in fabric production. After extraction, the fibers obtained will be short in length which will be twisted and made into a yarn of continuous length. The spinning process can vary depending on the desired yarn thickness and type (e.g., single, plied, or blended yarns). The bamboo yarn is then used to create fabrics through weaving or knitting processes.

Figure 2 – Production of Bamboo Fabric

- a. Cultivation of Bamboo, b. Soaking of Bamboo for fibre extraction, c. Bamboo Spun Fibre,
d. Bamboo Yarn, e. Bamboo Fabric

Image source – <https://www.guaduabamboo.com/blog/how-to-plant-bamboo>
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cElGZ4WF5Fs>

In case of bamboo fabric, after its production it undergoes various finishing to enhance its properties. Eg. Bamboo is known for its antimicrobial property which is mostly lost during the conversion of plant to fabric. Hence, after production, a coating of antimicrobial agent is usually done. In some cases, the fabric is also treated with softening agents to improve its drape and hand feel, making it softer and more comfortable against the skin. In addition to existing quality additional coating/ finishing is given to enhance the moisture management capabilities also. These treatments help to keep the fabric dry and comfortable by absorbing and wicking away moisture from the body.

To reduce the formation of pills (small fabric balls) on the surface of bamboo fabric, an anti-pilling treatment is given to maintain the fabric's smooth appearance and texture. When bamboo fabric is used for home textiles (bedding/upholstery) flame retardant finishes given help to improve its resistance to ignition and reduce flame spread [10]. Additionally, wrinkle-resistant finishes are given to reduce the formation of wrinkles and creases, making it easier to maintain a smooth and neat appearance.

On a similar note, antibacterial finishes are applied to the fabric to inhibit the growth of bacteria, thereby reducing odors and maintaining freshness [11]. Color fixation is also given to prevent color bleeding or fading. Other treatments include softening, dye fixation, and fabric stabilization based on the desired characteristics of the fabric [12, 13].

2.4 Properties of Bamboo textiles

It is identified that bamboo has 73% cellulose, 10% lignin, 12% hemicellulose, and for the textile use lignin and hemicellulose content should be reduced. Fabrics made from bamboo have properties similar to other regenerated cellulosic materials, such as viscose rayon, which are derived from wood (bast fibers). Bamboo fabric is known for its softness and luxurious feel, very similar to silk or cashmere wool in terms of its texture as well. Bamboo

fabric is highly breathable and moisture-wicking due to the presence of microgaps that enhance ventilation and moisture absorption [14]. Studies show that bamboo fabric has excellent thermal-regulating properties, which help in keeping the body cool in hot weather and warm in cooler temperatures, making it suitable for various climates [15,16] Research has identified that bamboo fiber has a higher moisture regain capability than cotton or other natural fibers, due to its loose structure and disordered noncellulose material [17].

Figure 3 – Properties of Bamboo Textile

In addition to feeling comfortable, the wearer is also protected by the natural antimicrobial agent called bamboo 'kun', which helps to prevent the growth of bacteria on the fabric, reducing odor and keeping it fresher for longer periods which also contribute to odor control making bamboo fabric a favorable choice for activewear or undergarments. The material is naturally hypoallergenic making it excellent choice for individuals with sensitive skin or allergies. It is also naturally resistant to dust mites and mold. It also provides natural UV protection, and has the ability to block a significant amount of harmful UV rays, offering an additional layer of sun protection [18]. Bamboo fabrics have been reported to have good soil release and twice the moisture absorbency compared to cotton. Due to the absence of free electrons, bamboo fabric is antistatic and has a good drape on the skin. Considering the amazing properties of bamboo (Fig.3), it is used in many applications that are expanding in all dimensions to meet the growing needs of the textile market.

2.5. The Diverse Applications of Bamboo Fiber

Bamboo has long been used for construction of home, furniture, as a writing material and even the biomass is used for bioethanol and biochar production [19]. In recent times bamboo has been used to make shopping bag, tote bag, gift wraps, and also in agro textiles such as like plant protection, erosion control, and weed suppression. Its application in textile and apparel are as follows;

Apparel and Fashion: Bamboo fabric is used to make a variety of garments, including t-shirts, dresses, skirts, underwear, socks, and activewear [20]. Its softness, breathability, and moisture-wicking properties make it comfortable for everyday wear and athletic activities. Considering the UV protection properties, apparels for pregnant women are made using bamboo to protect the mother from harmful radiation of sun's rays [21]. Accessories like scarves, hats, gloves, and socks are also made.

Intimate apparels: Bamboo is predominantly used in intimate apparels, as it is observed that bamboo fabrics are 1-2 degrees less than any other fabric type like cotton and linen. Bamboo fabrics are used to make underwear, bra, camisoles, tank tops, sleepwear, socks and leggings

Home Textiles: It is used as Mattresses, sanitary towels, table napkins, bags, curtain, television cover, sofa slipcover, bathrobes, bath towels, hand towels, shower curatins, bath mat, wash cloth, sheets, pillowcases, duvet covers, and blankets. Its softness and temperature-regulating properties contribute to a comfortable sleep environment. Bamboo is highly absorbent and quick-drying, making it suitable for bathroom textile products. It can be used to create lightweight and eco-friendly curtains and drapes for window treatments. [22]

Baby and Children's Products: The softness and hypoallergenic properties make it suitable for baby clothing, including onesies, pajamas, and bibs. It is sometimes used in cloth diapers due to its absorbency and antimicrobial properties.

Nonwovens: Considering the length of fiber, bamboo is used in paper-making industry and China having a long history on the same as early as 1700 years ago. Today compared to paper from wood, bamboo is less harmful [23]. It is also used in making of diapers, sanitary napkins, wipes, surgical gown, wound dressing, disposable bed sheets, cleaning wipes, mop heads and dishcloth.

Activewear and Sports: Considering the moisture-wicking and breathability qualities of bamboo sportswear, including workout tops, leggings, and sports bras can be designed. It is also used in outdoor clothing such as hiking shirts, pants, and jackets, due to its lightweight, moisture-wicking, and UV protective properties.

Interior Design: Bamboo fabric can be used for upholstery, cushions, and furniture coverings, adding a natural and eco-friendly touch to interior spaces. It is also applied as wall covering for decorative and sustainable purpose [24].

Medical and Healthcare: Bamboo fabric is used in some medical applications, including surgical gowns, wound dressings, masks, surgical clothes, nurses' wear, gauze mask and also as sanitary pads, sanitary towels, absorbent pads, toilet paper, tampons, menstrual underwear, reusable cloth pads, incontinence pads, panty liners and facial wipes. Its antimicrobial properties and hypoallergenic nature make it suitable for sensitive skin [25]. Recently sanitary napkins [26] and baby diapers made from bamboo have been reported to be very much welcoming in both urban and rural areas. Pre-folds and flat diapers is more commonly used as an absorbent insert in pocket diapers, all-in-one diapers, and hybrid diapers. The material is proven to be skin-safe and ecofriendly [27].

Smart Bamboo Textiles: Bamboo textiles are upgraded by using embedding sensors, microprocessors, and conductive threads for thermoregulation, moisture management, health monitoring, gesture control, energy harvesting (piezoelectric or solar cells into bamboo textiles) and interactive designs (LED lights or micro-displays) These textiles could change color, display patterns, or provide visual feedback based on user preferences or external stimuli.

2.6 Collaborative Efforts: Research Institutes and the Evolution of Bamboo Textiles

On understanding the applications of bamboo in textiles and fashion industry, it is significant to know the organisation/ research institutes who are actively engaged in research and development related to bamboo textiles.

Globally, International organisations include International Network for Bamboo and Rattan (INBAR), Bamboo and Rattan Research and Development Center (BARADECO), Forest Products Research and Development Institute (FPRDI) works and are channelled towards bamboo fiber extraction, textile innovation, and sustainable production practices. In India, Central Silk Board (CSB) is a statutory body under the Ministry of Textiles, Government of India, involved in research and development of various natural fibers, including bamboo, for textile applications. CSB has undertaken projects related to bamboo fiber extraction, processing, and fabric development. Bamboo Research and Training Centre (BRTC) in Kerala is a research and training institute focusing on bamboo and its applications. They conduct studies on bamboo textiles, including fiber extraction methods, fabric production, and product development. National Institute of Design has a 'Design Innovation Centre for Bamboo', where researchers and designers explore innovative applications of bamboo, including textiles. They focus on sustainable design practices and work towards promoting bamboo as a viable material in the textile industry. The Indian Plywood Industries Research and Training Institute (IPIRTI) work towards bamboo-based textile composites and Bamboo and Cane Development Institute (BCDI) in Agartala, Tripura works on development of bamboo and cane-based products and on improving the quality of bamboo textiles.

2.7. Bamboo: The Sustainable Choice for Brands

In addition to various initiatives by research organisations/ institutes, bamboo has been heavily marketed by various brands and designers for their product development. Bamboo has become recognized as an eco-friendly option compared to conventional textiles like cotton or synthetic fibers. Bamboo is often blended with other fibers, such as organic cotton or recycled polyester, to enhance its properties and create unique fabric blends. This allows for improved durability, increased stretch, or moisture-wicking capabilities.

Some of the prominent players include Beijing-based Tenbro Bamboo Textile, Bo Group (BoNa), China, Hebei Jigao Chemical Fiber Co., Ltd., China, Sichuan Holly North Industrial Co., Ltd., and Chengdu Grace Fiber Co., Ltd. well-known manufacturer of bamboo fiber and bamboo blended yarns. Today, despite China's continued dominance in the textile industry, the United States remains the primary source of bamboo textiles.

Some of the interesting product categories are done by Eco HY (China) the brand specializing in the production of biodegradable dinnerware manufactured from bamboo fibers. Beco (Mumbai, India) a startup has been creating kitchen towel and trash bag from Bamboo and corn starch polymer. Ettitude is a brand based in Los Angeles, US to launch sleep wear and bedding items from bamboo which has reported to raise USD 1.6 million sales as per May 2020 [27] suggesting the application of bamboo in today's market to be extremely profitable.

Some other clothing and textile brands (Fig.4) working with bamboo are;

Cariloha – an US based brand comes with the tagline ‘comfy way to save planet’ that converts bamboo field into bamboo viscose fabrics for bedding, bath, apparel to create green fabrics.

Thought clothing - UK based brand has various product category like bamboo underwear, Socks, bamboo loungewear, leggings, tops, apparel that matches that sustainability goals.

TASC Performance, New Orleans-based company was started with the objective of ‘reinventing performance apparel’ using a new kind of patented concept in fabric finishing process called BamCo®, that result in anti-odor, comfort properties, durability, easy care and maintenance.

Bamboo tribe is an Indian brand that promotes their well-tailored wardrobe staples highlighting that conventional polyester based activewear can release 2808 bags of microplastics to the ocean every year.

Nature fab is yet another Indian brand that manufactures underwear, tees, pjs, leggings, towels, face mask and various other performance apparel using natural dyes with bamboo marketing their material as the softest fabric on earth.

Figure 4 – Popular Brands using Bamboo Fibre

Apart from these brands Bam Bamboo clothing, Komodo, Thought, LNBF, Zen bamboo, Spun bamboo and Onno offer sustainable clothing solutions using bamboo.

2.8. The Green Truth: Sustainability Facts about Bamboo

Understanding how many brands are commercially successful, there are also remarks questioning how much bamboo is sustainable and environment friendly. The production of bamboo involves use of chemicals that can harm the environment as in the manufacturing of rayon from wood pulp. The conversion of bamboo into textile fibers often involves chemical processes. Depending on the specific manufacturing methods used, these processes may introduce potentially harmful chemicals and impact the sustainability of the final product. Consumers increasingly seek transparency and look for certified bamboo products. The flip side is bamboo doesn't contribute to deforestation considering the way it is removed (base stalk retained). Bamboo is also better than cotton because it is not a water and pesticide dependant crop and definitely a better alternative.

When a designer/ manufacturer is looking for sustainable options, it is better to look for materials with low carbon footprint in the overall processing rather than a 100% eco-friendly considering the real time challenges in creating something completely sustainable. To ensure a lower carbon footprint in bamboo, it is advisable to look for bamboo textile products that are sourced sustainably, manufactured using energy-efficient processes, and have transparent supply chains. In order to ensure the sustainability of bamboo textile products, certifications such as the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) or the Oeko-Tex Standard, which provide assurance that the textiles meet specific environmental and social criteria throughout their production process can be verified. In future, mechanical processing methods that reduce chemical usage, use of closed-loop systems, more sustainable chemicals, and water-saving technologies can make bamboo 100% ecofriendly [28].

Understanding the significance and amazing properties of bamboo, the study was planned to use the source bamboo and create an ensemble for summer.

3. Exploring eco-friendly printing techniques

As a process of value addition dyeing or printing is done to the textile surface. In the rise of minimalism and slow fashion, localised dyeing namely printing was adopted. In this context, safe and ecofriendly methods of printing were studied and documented as below.

3.1 Hand pounding

It is a technique that involves physically pounding or hammering the fresh flowers onto the fabric to release their natural dyes and create unique designs. A protective layer, such as a thin cloth or plastic wrap are kept over the flowers to prevent them from sticking to the pounding tool. Materials like wooden mallet, hammer, or similar tool is used for pounding the flowers, the pressure and force applied should be sufficient to release the pigments but too much that it can damage the fabric. In this method of eco printing the flowers/leaves are placed with white space in between them. In most cases only half the fabric is covered with plants and the other half is folded on top followed by a cover. Later the flowers are pounded with a hammer, hard enough as to absorb the dye from plants. After the bashing, the fabric will be opened to remove plants and to let it to air dry.

3.2. Bundle dyeing

Bundle dyeing involves bundling plant materials, along with the fabric, to create a package. This bundle is then steamed or simmered, allowing the colors to extract from the plants and transfer onto the fabric. In the process, the plant materials may or may not directly contact the fabric. Bundle dyeing often produces abstract or diffused patterns, as the colors spread and blend during the steaming or simmering, resulting in a soft and organic appearance. In bundle dyeing, the plant materials can be enclosed within the bundle, often sandwiched between layers of fabric or secured with string or fabric wraps.

Figure 5 – Hand pounding, Bundle dyeing and Eco-printing
Image source: The barefootdyer & Marta Mouka /Instagram

3.3. Ecoprinting

Eco-printing, on the other hand, entails placing plant materials such as leaves or flowers directly onto the fabric. Pressure is applied, usually through pounding or rolling, to transfer the colors and patterns from the plants onto the fabric. The patterns in eco-printing are more defined and closely resemble the shape and structure of the plant materials used. The direct contact and pressure allow for more precise and detailed patterns on the fabric. In eco-printing, the plant materials are placed directly on the fabric, leaving space between them to facilitate color and pattern transfer. When it comes to colorfastness, bundle dyeing generally yields more durable results. The dyes extracted from the plants are fixed onto the fabric through the heat and moisture of the steaming or simmering process. On the other hand, eco-printing may produce less colorfast outcomes, as the dyes from the plants are transferred through direct contact and pressure, which may not provide the same level of color fixation. Both bundle dyeing and eco-printing offer unique ways to incorporate natural colors and patterns into fabrics, providing opportunities for creative expression and sustainable dyeing practices [29].

3.3.1 Steps in eco-printing

It begins by collecting leaves, flowers, and stems to create a print from natural sources. These plant materials contain pigments that can be transferred to fabric through a printing process. The fabric to be printed is typically pre-treated to improve dye absorption. This is done by the process of mordanting, which is the process of treating the fabric with natural substances to enhance its print quality. Mordants play a key role in fixing of plant pigment on the surface of the textile, intensity of the print color and permanency of the print.

3.3.2 Commonly used Mordants for eco-printing

Depending on the fabric selected for study, mordants are chosen. Generally, cotton, linen, requires intense mordanting as the fabric cannot readily take up natural dye. Myrobalan works well for cotton and alum for silk. Wool is the best fiber to be used for natural dyeing, and silk is the next option to get the best shades using natural sources. Synthetic textiles, do not have the ability to uptake nor hold back the natural dyes/pigments due to its chemical nature. There are different mordants used for ecoprinting namely;

- Alum/ Potassium Aluminum Sulfate is one of the safe and most commonly used mordants that helps in fixing and to intensify the colors, particularly on cellulose fibers like cotton and linen. It is ideal for silk and wool based fiber compositions.
- Iron/ Iron Sulfate/ Ferrous Sulfate is used to shift colors and create grey or black tones, darken and deepen any natural colors. These are usually used in small quantities as it can overpower other colors if used excessively. The effluent containing iron is also not disposed of to the plants immediately as it can be harmful.
- Copper/ Copper Sulfate can produce green hues and help in obtaining color variations, but should be used with caution as it is carcinogenic in nature.
- Soy milk is a natural binder and mordant that can help improve colorfastness in ecoprinting often used in combination with other mordants.
- Tannins are natural substances found in various plant materials and are often used as a mordant in ecoprinting. Examples include oak galls, tea leaves, pomegranate skins, banana skin, myrobalan, onion skin and tamarind. The use of these can enhance the colorfastness and create deeper and more durable prints.

3.3.3 Natural materials for eco-printing

- **Marigold flowers** are widely appreciated in ecoprinting due to their vibrant yellow and orange hues. They can create lovely, intricate patterns on fabric.
- **Dahlia flowers** offer a wide range of colors, including vibrant reds, pinks, and purples
- **Roses** come in various colors and can add elegance to ecoprinted fabrics. Different rose varieties yield different shades, ranging from deep reds to soft pinks.
- **Geraniums** are known for their vibrant and diverse colors, such as red, pink, and purple
- **Coreopsis flowers** is a very popular material for ecoprinting and can offer shades of yellow, gold, and orange
- **Black-eyed Susan** flowers have vibrant yellow petals with dark brown centers
- **Eucalyptus leaves** are widely cherished in ecoprinting due to their high tannin content, which can result in rich, deep prints. They can yield shades of reddish-brown, orange, and green.
- **Maple leaves** are known for their distinct shapes and can create intricate veining patterns when used in ecoprinting. They often produce shades of yellow, orange, and brown.
- **Oak leaves** are appreciated for their strong tannin content, resulting in deep, earthy tones, shades of brown, rust, and green.
- **Rose leaves** can contribute to delicate and elegant prints not in red but in soft green hues
- **Ivy leaves** offer unique shapes and textures with various shades of green and sometimes exhibit veining patterns as well
- **Geranium leaves** give green shade with distinct shapes and can create interesting patterns on fabric.

3.3.4 Process of eco-printing

In the process of ecoprinting, carefully selected raw materials are arranged on the fabric in a deliberate pattern or design. The aim is to achieve optimal contact between the plant materials and the fabric surface. To ensure this, the fabric is tightly bundled and secured. Subsequently, the bundled fabric undergoes either a steaming or boiling process, enabling the extraction of pigments from the plant materials and their transfer onto the fabric. The application of heat plays a crucial role in releasing the natural dyes and facilitating their absorption by the fabric fibers, resulting in vibrant colors. Once the printing process is complete, the fabric is left to dry. Excess plant

materials are then removed, and the fabric often undergoes a thorough washing to eliminate any residual pigments or impurities, ensuring a clean and refined final product [30].

3.3.5 Surface manipulation and eco-printing

Ecoprinting offers a wide range of possibilities for enhancing the aesthetics of fabric through the integration of various techniques. By incorporating techniques such as accordion folds, pleating, or spiral wrapping, diverse and captivating designs can be achieved, adding an element of visual interest to the ecoprinted fabric. Additionally, fabric manipulation techniques like pleating, shirring, or folding can be employed to introduce captivating textural effects. Another approach to further enhance the design exploration is through resist techniques, which create contrast and negative space. This can be achieved by applying natural wax or utilizing objects such as rubber bands or wooden blocks to create resist patterns prior to ecoprinting. To deepen or shift the colors in the prints, color modifiers like iron or copper mordants can be utilized, introducing unique and complex effects. Furthermore, after the ecoprinting process, the fabric can be enriched with hand embroidery or embellishments, including threads, beads, or sequins. These additional elements serve to enhance and complement the organic patterns created by ecoprinting, resulting in a truly captivating and unique final product [31].

3.3.6 Tests for ecoprinted fabric

In order to ensure the quality of the ecoprinted fabric various tests can be performed as discussed below;

pH Testing ensures that the fabric is within an acceptable pH range, as extreme pH levels can affect the fabric's durability and potentially cause skin irritation.

Colorfastness to Washing is washing the fabric according to specific standards, and any color bleeding or fading is observed and noted. Using the standard color scale the acceptance/ rejection is decided.

Colorfastness to Light is done by exposing the sample to simulated sunlight for a specified period, and to document any noticeable color changes.

Rubbing Fastness is done by rubbing the printed fabric against a white fabric or rubbing cloth, and to examine any color transfer or staining on the white/undyed/control sample.

Tear Strength is a test to measure the fabric's resistance to tearing. It helps determine the durability of the ecoprinted fabric and its ability to withstand normal wear and tear.

Seam Strength evaluates the strength of the seams in the ecoprinted fabric. It measures the force required to break or separate the seams, ensuring they are strong and secure.

Pilling Resistance assesses the fabric's resistance to pilling, indicating its ability to maintain a smooth and neat appearance. Here Pill refers to the formation of small balls of fibers on the fabric surface.

Dimensional Stability determines how well the fabric retains its shape and size after washing or other treatments. It measures any changes in the fabric's dimensions, such as shrinkage or stretching.

3.3.7 Care and maintenance of ecoprinted textiles

To ensure the longevity and preservation of ecoprinted textiles, it is recommended to follow specific care instructions. Generally, these textiles are best washed using mild detergent or pH neutral soap, or alternatively, traditional reetha nut can be used. Hand washing is preferable to maintain the delicate nature of the prints. When drying, it is advisable to opt for a shaded area to prevent any potential fading of the print caused by exposure to direct sunlight. When ironing ecoprinted textiles, it is important to use a mild temperature setting and place a layer of newspaper or butter paper between the fabric and the iron. This precaution helps to prevent the print from fading or getting damaged due to excessive heat during the ironing process. By adhering to these care guidelines, the beauty and integrity of the ecoprinted textiles can be preserved for an extended period.

3.3.8 Brands working on Eco-printing

The famous artists/ brand working with ecoprinting techniques on textiles and leather are The Bare foot dyer (Austin, Texas), Marta Mouka (Canada), Flora obscura by Alison Kelly, Earthues (Washington, USA), Fibershed (California), Ecopalette (India), The Colours of Nature (Tamil Nadu), Craftroots (India), Dastkar (NPO) (New Delhi), Kalhath Institute (Andhra Pradesh), Colorashram foundation, Econic India and Terrieakwong (Ecoprinting on leather).

These brands showcase many experiments, research design, working with artisans, collaborate with natural dyers, local communities to promote sustainable textile production methods.

4. Study on creating an ensemble for summer using bamboo and value addition through ecoprinting

As a design project bamboo fabric was purchased and ecoprinted for value addition. It was planned to construct an ensemble for summer, which has become a need considering the global climatic issues/ ozone depletion and harsh summers. Objective of the study was to create a comfortable and breezy ensemble for a women clientele who is between the age group of 15 to 25years.

4.1. Sourcing of the fabric

Bamboo was selected for the considering its amazing benefits on skin and for hot climates to tackle heat and sweat. Woven bamboo fabric was purchased from the website 'Suvetah' (<https://suvetah.com>). The fabric had 140 GSM, 58' width and fabric count of 40S x 40S and priced at 4.27 USD per meter. (Fig.6)

Figure 6 – Eco-printing 100% Bamboo Fabric using Marigold Petals

- a. Mordanted Bamboo with alum, b. Patterning for eco-printing using marigold petals
c. Bundling for steaming, d. Eco-printed Fabric

4.2. Preparing the fabric for ecoprinting

Purchased 3 meters of bamboo fabric was treated with 64 gms of alum for 30mins to commence the process of mordanting. After the process, excess water was squeezed and fabric was allowed to semi-dry which took 3 hrs. The semidried mordanted fabric is then laid on a flat surface and petals are placed by random lay.

Figure 7 – Prepared Flat sketch, Specifications sheet and Product shoot

Ensemble for summer made using marigold petal eco-printed on 100% Bamboo

4.3 Preparing the printing material for ecoprinting

Marigold flowers offered to deity after worship is thrown away. This was collected from the temples to be used for the study and weighed approximately 0.5 kg. Here the petals can be placed randomly, as sandwich, or in patterns. For the study, pattern placements were used.

4.4 Process of printing

After placements, a plastic wrap or cloth is used to hold the elements in place, and then rolled up tightly, which is later secured with a string to hold the shape. The fabric bundle was kept in a steamer basket and steamed for 1-2 hours to extract the dye from the marigold petal to fabric. In some cases, boiling is tried, where the fabric bundle is kept in a pot filled with enough water to submerge it, boiled and simmered for 1-2 hours.

4.5 Cooling and Unwrapping: It is done after steaming, where the bundle is allowed to cool. The unwrap of fabric is done, and marigold petals are carefully removed (Fig.6).

4.6 Finishing: Rinsing is done using cold water to remove any excess dye or plant residue. The fabric is gently squeezed to remove excess water, dried in shade. The marigold flower eco-printing process can result in vibrant yellow and orange prints, capturing the essence of the marigold plant.

4.7 Designing ensemble for summer: The eco-printed bamboo fabric was used to make a summer frock for clientele in the age group of 15-20 years. The process began by taking measurements, creating the spec sheet, considering the age group, season, personality and economical status. The fit, wash and wear parameters were reported to be good and acceptable for the client.

5. Conclusion

Bamboo is often touted as a sustainable and eco-friendly fabric due to its rapid growth and minimal need for pesticides or fertilizers. Understanding the progress of the selected textiles in the market, bamboo was selected for the study and eco-printing was done to celebrate the natural world on a wearer. The fabric designed was extremely comfortable with no color bleeding, after the post mordanted treatment with alum and fixing of the print with hot steaming after a week. The ensemble is expected to have less carbon footprint than conventional textiles and perform better than them.

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